

MODELING RESIN INFUSION OF COMPLEX SHAPE TEXTILE PREFORMS DURING THE VARTM PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding (VARTM) has been developed as a variant of the traditional Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) process. It offers numerous cost advantages such as lower tooling cost, shorter start-up time, and the use of a preform that enables the incorporation of many components into a single part, thus reducing both the cost and weight of the structure. These features make VARTM attractive for the manufacture of large and complex composite components. However, a great deal of work still needs to be done to reduce the costly trial-and-error methods of the VARTM processing that are currently in practice today. A comprehensive computer simulation package of VARTM process has been developed in this study. The model includes three submodels: the viscosity and cure kinetics of the resin, the resin flow in the porous reinforcement preform, and the compaction of the preform during the infiltration procedure. A unique feature of the computer code is the ability to integrate the use of 1-D, 2-D and 3-D element types in a single simulation, and thus enables efficient modeling of the complex mold geometries. In this investigation, the resin infiltration of a three-stiffener carbon fiber preform by the VARTM process was simulated using the computer code. The objective was to study the resin flow and compaction of the preform during the VARTM of a complex shaped part. The computer model was used to analyze the flow details, track the thickness change of the preform, and predict the total infiltration time and final fiber volume fraction of the part.

KEY WORDS: VARTM, simulation, resin flow, compaction

INTRODUCTION

Vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) has shown potential to reduce the manufacturing cost of composite structures. Recent studies have demonstrated that carbon fiber preforms can be resin infiltrated by the VARTM process and cured to produce void free structures with fiber volume fractions approaching 58% [1]. The manufacture of composite structures by the VARTM process requires the specification of numerous molding and processing parameters. The use of empirical trial-and-error methods to determine these parameters would be both time consuming and costly. A computer simulation model of the VARTM process would provide a cost-effective tool in the manufacturing of composites utilizing this technique.

Two important issues must be considered in the simulation of the VARTM process. These include resin flow in the preform and the compaction behavior of the preform. Previous investigations that have addressed these two mechanisms are summarized as follows.

Hsiao et al. [2] proposed a closed form solution for resin flow in the distribution medium and fiber mat during the VARTM process. A parametric study was conducted to investigate the influence of a number of process variables on the infiltration time. It was found that the fill time decreases when the thickness of the distribution medium relative to that of the preform increases. The porosity of the distribution medium was found not to affect the infiltration time. The infiltration time was found to be much more sensitive to the permeability of the distribution medium than that of the preform. Tari et al. [3] investigated the effect of the high permeable distribution medium on the resin flow field in VARTM through analysis, simulation and experiment. This study showed that the use of distribution medium creates a transverse flow in the fiber mat and thus greatly reduces preform infiltration time. The importance of the distribution medium in mold filling was experimentally investigated by Sun et al. [4]. The results showed that the use of the distribution medium reduced the infiltration time by 85%. Sun et al. employed a 3D control volume/finite element model for the numerical simulation of the resin infusion process. The numerical results for the infiltration time compared well with the experimental measurements. Neglecting in-plane resin flow in the preform, the authors presented a 2D leakage flow model, which considered in-plane flow in the distribution medium and a sink term to account for the resin leaking into the preform. The leakage flow model reduced the computational cost significantly and yet provided a reasonable estimate of the preform infiltration time.

In the VARTM process, the flexible nature of the vacuum bag, coupled with varying pressure inside the mold cavity, produces laminates with a non-uniform thicknesses. Rigas et al.[5] investigated variations of the thickness in composite parts manufactured by the VARTM process. Panels were fabricated using a 22-ply S2 glass, plain weave fabric. Final part thickness was measured at different locations after the part was fully cured. It was found that the final cured thickness of a part varies along the resin progression direction. As the distance from the vacuum source increases, the part thickness increases. The thickness variation across the panel was close to 6%. Williams et al. [6] performed a preliminary experimental study of fabric compression during VARTM processing. The compaction of the reinforcement was found to be very complex. An initial reduction in thickness under vacuum was observed. The presence of the flowing resin appeared to have a lubricating effect and resulted in a further compaction. However, since the net pressure on the laminate fell after the passage of the resin, the preform thickness subsequently increased. Detailed knowledge of the response of reinforcing fabrics subjected to compressive forces is very important in the investigation of the dynamic compaction behavior of the preform. However, past investigations in reinforcement compaction were mainly carried out for the RTM process where the compaction pressure can reach 1 MPa. Only a few investigations [5-8] on the compression behavior of the reinforcement during VARTM, i.e., under low compaction pressure (≤ 1 atm) were published. It was found that by mechanically loading and unloading the preform, a maximum fiber volume fraction may be attained prior to applying vacuum for resin infusion [5]. Under the same pressure, the fiber samples saturated with resin are compacted more than the dry reinforcements due to the lubrication effect of the resin. Hammami and Gebart [8] proposed a 1-D model to simulate the VARTM process considering both the resin flow and the compaction of the preform. In this model, Darcy's law and the continuity equation were used to model the resin flow, and an equation of transverse equilibrium was introduced to take into account the compaction of the preform under the vacuum force. Compared with the infusion experiments, the model obtained a good estimate of the total infiltration time in the VARTM process. However, the authors did not present any results on the thickness change of the preform during the infusion process.

In the present investigation, a finite element model was developed to simulate resin infiltration of a three-stiffener preform by the VARTM process. The objective was to study both the resin flow and thickness changes in a complex shaped preform.

VARTM MODEL FORMULATION

The simulation model consists of three coupled submodels: the resin flow in the porous reinforcement preform, the compaction of the preform during the infiltration procedure, and the viscosity and cure kinetics of the resin.

The flow model is developed to track the flow of the resin through the distribution medium and the preform. Both the high-permeable distribution medium and the preform can be modeled as heterogeneous and anisotropic porous media. The resin fluid is assumed to be Newtonian and incompressible. Assuming that the flow is quasi-steady-state, the governing equations for the flow problem are the continuity equation for an incompressible fluid, and Darcy's law:

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{v} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\vec{v} = \frac{\vec{q}}{\phi} = -\frac{S}{\phi\mu} \nabla P_r \quad (2)$$

where, \vec{v} is the interstitial velocity vector of the resin, \vec{q} the superficial velocity vector, ϕ the porosity of the porous preform, μ the viscosity of the resin, S the permeability tensor of the preform, and P_r is the resin pressure.

The boundary conditions necessary to solve the governing equations are:

- A flow front pressure condition: $P_{r_{flow\ front}} = 0$
- A constant pressure condition at the inlet: $P_{r_{inlet}} = \hat{P}_r$
- The velocity normal to the mold wall and vacuum bag is zero: $\vec{v} \cdot \vec{n} = 0$, where \vec{n} is the vector normal to the boundary wall.

In addition to the governing equations deriving the flow model, i.e., Darcy's law and the continuity equation, a new equation is introduced to account for the transverse equilibrium inside the mold cavity during impregnation [7]:

$$P = P_r + P_n \quad (3)$$

where, P is the total compaction pressure ($\approx 1\text{atm}$), P_r is the resin pressure, and P_n is the net pressure applied on the preform.

At each time step, after the calculation of the resin pressure distribution, the net pressure applied on the preform is computed using eqn. 3. Then the normal strain in the transverse direction, ε , can be obtained from the curves of strain .vs. compression pressure, which are the results of the compaction test. With the initial fiber volume fraction of the preform (V_{f_0}) and thickness of the panel (t_0) given, the displacement (w), thickness (t) and fiber volume fraction (V_f) can be found by the eqns. 4, 5, and 6, respectively.

$$w = \int_0^{t_0} \varepsilon ds \quad (4)$$

$$t = t_0 + w \quad (5)$$

$$V_f = V_{f_0} \frac{t_0}{t} \quad (6)$$

The resin viscosity and cure kinetics are important for the accurate simulation of the infusion process and to determine whether the preform can be infiltrated before resin gelation. The resin used in this study is the SI-ZG-5A epoxy resin developed at A.T.A.R.D laboratories. The resin cure kinetics and viscosity models obtained by Grimsley et al. [9] are used in this study.

COMPACTION TEST

The relationship between the strain in the preform and pressure applied was obtained from compaction test data. Details of the compaction experimental procedures can be found in reference 10. Compaction tests were conducted to measure the displacements of an unstitched multi-axial warp knitted fabric under low pressures experienced during the VARTM process. Because of the resin lubrication effect, the compression response of the wet fibrous preform was found to be quite different from that of the dry fiber mat. The hysteresis phenomenon was observed during the unloading process. At the start of the infusion process, the dry reinforcement is under the vacuum compression and the strain of the preform can be calculated from the compaction response of the dry preform during the loading process. As resin infuses into the preform, the local net pressure applied to the preform decreases as a result of increasing resin pressure. This is equivalent to an unloading process. Accordingly, the strain in the wet preform is determined by compaction response of the resin-saturated preform during the unloading process. The equation of preform strain as a function of pressure for the 4-stacks of unstitched multi-axial warp knit fabric, supplied by SAERTEX is given as follows,

$$\varepsilon = \begin{cases} 0.24(1 - \exp(-0.025P_n)) & \text{dry compaction, loading} \\ 0.082 + 0.24 \frac{P_n}{3.82 + P_n} & \text{wet compaction, unloading} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where, ε is the strain of the preform, and P_n is the net pressure applied to the preform.

SIMULATION RESULTS

In this study, VARTM of a three-stiffener panel using SAERTEX multi-axial non-crimp carbon fiber fabric and the SI-ZG-5A epoxy resin [9] was studied. The preform is shown in Fig. 1 and consisted of a 60.96 cm long by 60.96 cm wide by 1.43 cm thick skin, and three 9.05 cm high by 1.91 cm thick stiffeners. The stiffeners were flared out at the bottom in order to create a flange that was equal to half the thickness of the preform material. Each flange was then stitched to the skin, forming a preform. The thermophysical and flow properties used in the simulation are given in reference 11.

A schematic diagram of the infusion scheme is shown in Fig. 2. During the VARTM process, the injection occurs through the resin ports on the skin of the preform, and vacuum is pulled through the ports on the top of the stiffeners. The distribution medium is laid on the preform skin to enhance the resin flow in the preform and reduce the infiltration time.

Table 1 Size and predicted infiltration times. Case C is assumed to be the exact solution.

Case	Nodes	Elements	Fill time (min)	Error %
A	295	224	139.1	-5.57
B	498	398	146.3	-0.68
C	538	422	147.3	-

Figure 1 Three-stiffener carbon fiber preform

Figure 2 Infusion scheme for the VARTM of three-stiffener preform

The geometry of the three-stiffener carbon fiber preform is uniform along the length of the preform. Therefore, the resin velocity in the length direction is negligible, and the resin flow during the VARTM process is reduced to a two-dimensional problem. Due to the symmetry, only half of the domain was

included in the simulation models. For the two-dimensional simulation, a 4-noded rectangular element was used to construct the finite element mesh. Three finite element models with increasing mesh density were constructed to find a converged model for the simulation. The number of nodes and elements, and the infiltration time predicted by each model are listed in Table 1. It is shown that the meshes have converged for the flow model. The calculated time varied by only 0.68% between Case B and Case C, therefore, the results of Case C can be used as the 'true' solution of the finite element model. The mesh of Case C is illustrated in Fig. 3.

The simulated flow pattern is shown in Fig. 4. It is noted that the resin quickly filled the skin and then slowly propagated up the stiffeners. The predicted shape of the flow front in the stiffener was flat, which indicates that the stiffener infiltration process was essentially one-dimensional. Consequently, the tops of the stiffeners were the last points of the preform to be infiltrated. This result confirmed the correct choice for the location of the vents or vacuum ports to infiltrate the complex preform adequately. The total infiltration time was calculated to be 147 minutes. Fig. 5 shows the details of the resin flow in the preform skin. Resin infiltrates the skin rapidly due to the presence of the high permeability distribution media on the top surfaces of the skin and a resin inlet port at each distribution medium. The total infiltration time for the skin was approximately 7.7 minutes, which represented 5.2% of the preform total infiltration time.

The preform displacements in y direction (see Fig. 3) were calculated at the three points, which were located on the top of the skin (u_{skin}), flange (u_{flange}), and stiffener ($u_{stiffener}$), respectively. The evolution of the displacements during the infiltration process is shown in Figures 6-8. Before the infiltration process began, the dry preform was compacted under full vacuum pressure. When the resin flowed into the preform, at all the monitored locations, a small compaction of the preform (positive displacement) occurred due to the resin lubrication effect. However, a large springback (negative displacement) followed shortly because the lubrication effect was quickly overcome by the springback phenomenon corresponding to the increase in local resin pressure. For the skin and the flange, after the maximum amount of springback was achieved, the displacement remained constant at -2.25 mm and -3.2 mm, respectively. The amount of springback observed caused a reduction in the skin and flange final fiber volume fraction to a value of 43.6%. In the stiffener, the resin propagated slowly and the wetting deformation mechanism weakened the effect of the springback mechanism slightly. Therefore, the stiffener displacement increased gradually after the maximum amount of the springback was achieved after about 45 minutes. When the resin reached the top of the stiffener at about 140 minutes, another sharp decrease in the stiffener displacement occurred, but the amount of the preform springback was relatively small. The magnitude of the springback observed in the stiffener was significantly lower compared to the flange and the skin. Consequently, the final stiffener fiber volume fraction was higher and reached an average value of 51%.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a comprehensive simulation model was used to investigate the VARTM process of a three-stiffener preform. A mesh refinement study was performed to find a converged finite element model and achieve an accurate prediction of the resin flow and compaction in the preform. The results of the simulation showed that the distribution medium and resin inlet ports were correctly located on the preform to allow complete resin infiltration of the preform. The use of the highly permeable distribution medium on the top surface of the skin allowed the resin to quickly infiltrate the preform skin. In the stiffeners, no distribution medium was used and hence resin infiltration was very slow. Significant springback of the preform occurred during the injection process because the springback mechanism dominated over the wetting deformation mechanism as a result of increasing resin pressure.

Figure 3 Finite element mesh for Case C

Figure 4 Flow front progression (in seconds) predicted by Case C

Figure 5 Predicted flow front progression in the skin for the first 7.7 minutes (464 seconds) of the infiltration

Figure 6 Predicted skin vertical displacement (u_{skin}) for the different meshes

Figure 7 Predicted flange vertical displacement (u_{flange}) for the different meshes

Figure 8 Predicted stiffener vertical displacement ($u_{stiffener}$) for the different meshes

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The research at Virginia Tech was supported by NASA Langley Research Center under Research Cooperative Agreement NCC-1-01037. The project monitor is Mr. Roberto J. Cano.

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